

THE ARTISTIC REFLECTION OF HISTORICAL FIGURES IN NIZAMI GANJAVI’S “KHAMSA”

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ABSTRACT. *Nizami Ganjavi, who lived in the city of Ganja during the twelfth and thirteenth centuries, reflected in his poems various meetings, relations, and correspondences with prominent historical figures of his era. Among them were the rulers of the Atabeg state, Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan and Qizil Arslan, the ruler of Maragha from the Aghsunqid dynasty Alaaddin Korpe Arslan, the Shirvanshah ruler Akhsitan I, the ruler of Derbent Dara Muzaffaraddin, the renowned architect Ajami Nakhchivani, and the distinguished poet Afzaladdin Khagani Shirvani.*

The literary heritage of Nizami, regarded as one of the peaks of world literature, also served as a major source of inspiration for Eastern miniature art. The illustrated manuscript copies of his works frequently depict scenes connected with his relationships and encounters with these historical personalities. Such miniatures not only demonstrate the artistic richness of the manuscripts but also preserve important aspects of the political and cultural environment of medieval Azerbaijan.

Historical sources indicate that the poet’s first wife, Afag, was sent to him by the ruler of Derbent, while the Atabeg ruler granted Nizami fifteen thousand dinars and four villages. Likewise, Akhsitan I commissioned the poet to compose Layla and Majnun. The first part of Iskandarnama was dedicated to the Atabeg ruler Nusrataddin Abu Bakr, while the second part was presented to the Seljuk ruler Izzaddin Masud. These facts clearly demonstrate Nizami Ganjavi’s close relations with the political and cultural elites of his time and reflect the great respect shown toward the poet by contemporary rulers.

Keywords: *Nizami Ganjavi, Khamsa, poet and rulers, Atabays, Shirvanshahs, Saljuqs, Ganja.*

INTRODUCTION

For centuries, the Azerbaijani people have contributed outstanding personalities to world literature and culture. Among them, the great poet Nizami Ganjavi, who gained worldwide fame through his collection of poems known as the “Khamsa,” occupies a special place. The historical approach to Nizami’s personality, as well as information regarding his meetings and correspondence with prominent historical figures of his era — including poets, architects, and rulers — are for the first time being comprehensively examined within the framework of this scholarly research.

Nizami, who lived in the city of Ganja in Azerbaijan during the late twelfth and early thirteenth centuries, provided in his poems certain information about his meetings and correspondence with a number of influential personalities of the period. Among them were the

famous architect Ajami Nakhchivani, the Atabeg rulers Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan and Qizil Arslan, the ruler of Maragha Alaaddin Korpe Arslan, the Shirvanshah ruler Akhsitan I, the ruler of Derbent Dara Muzaffaraddin, as well as the distinguished poets Afzaladdin Khagani Shirvani and

An Overview of the Historical Period in Which Nizami Ganjavi Lived

When examining the history of Azerbaijan in the eleventh and twelfth centuries, it becomes evident that the period was relatively stable and prosperous, while rulers sought to demonstrate their power by gathering poets, architects, and astronomers around them. In his work, Mammad Amin Rasulzade compares Shirvan during the reign of Manuchehr Akhsitan to Ghazna under Sultan Mahmud on a smaller scale, noting that Shirvan (Shamakhi), as an important trade center, was famous for its architectural monuments, gardens, and parks. [1, 46].

The city of Ganja, where the poet was born and spent his entire life, was likewise one of the major cultural centers of the country. After the destruction of the city of Barda by foreign invaders, Ganja developed even further and remained under the constant attention of the Azerbaijani Atabegs. According to the Arab historian Istakhri, nearly 300,000 inhabitants perished during the earthquake that struck Ganja in 1139. This fact demonstrates the scale and significance of the ancient city as a major urban center. [1, 47].

In order to gain a broader understanding of the literary environment of that period, it is useful to refer to Rasulzade's work *Azerbaijani Poet Nizami*, published in exile in 1941. The author mentions several prominent literary figures of the age: Abul-Ula Ganjavi, who served in the courts of the Shirvanshahs Manuchehr and Akhsitan before later moving to Ganja; Afzaladdin Khagani Shirvani, renowned for his qasida describing Shirvanshah Akhsitan's victory against Russian invaders and also known for his poems dedicated to Qizil Arslan; and Falaki Shirvani, a court poet as well as a distinguished astronomer whose poetry frequently employed metaphors connected with stars and celestial bodies. Among other notable figures were Mujir Beylagani, who dedicated qasidas to the Atabeg rulers Eldiguz and Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan; Seyid Zulfugar Shirvani; Mahsati Ganjavi; and many other poets and scholars who appeared like shining stars adorning the literary sky of the period. [1, 43].

Meetings of Nizami Ganjavi with the Rulers of His Time

In Khosrow and Shirin, while describing his meeting with Qizil Arslan, Nizami writes:

"Whenever fate granted me the opportunity to speak,
I uttered such words that the state itself approved them." [2, 141].

Nizami dedicated each of his literary works to a ruler and sent them to royal courts. By doing so, the poet sought recognition for his творчество while also believing that such patronage would ensure the preservation of his works throughout history. During that period, palace libraries carried out extensive work in preserving manuscripts and reproducing them in elegant copies. Furthermore, the wider the geographical circulation of these manuscripts, the greater their influence and dissemination became. [3, 93].

Among the Shirvanshahs, Akhsitan I aimed to strengthen not only the political but also the literary and cultural life of his state. He invited hundreds of poets to his court; however, his attempt to establish a literary assembly in Shirvan proved unsuccessful because of rivalry among poets such as Afzaladdin Khagani Shirvani, Abul-Ula Ganjavi, and Mujiraddin Beylagani. As a consequence of these conflicts, Abul-Ula left the palace and moved to Ganja, Khagani was imprisoned while attempting to flee, and Mujiraddin escaped to Tabriz before being exiled to

Isfahan. Observing these events, Nizami once again refused Akhsitan's invitation and chose not to join the royal court. Instead, he continued his literary activity in Ganja, where he attracted numerous intellectuals and artists around him. A literary circle was eventually formed in the city, and within a short period famous poets such as Amir Muizzi and Asiraddin Ferganali were invited to Azerbaijan. [2,141]. The arrival of Zahiraddin Farabi and other Central Asian poets in Ganja further demonstrated the respect and appreciation shown by the Atabeg rulers toward literature and scholars. [4, 68].

Academician Ziya Bunyadov notes that the first work included in Nizami's "Khamisa" was dedicated to the ruler of Erzincan, Fakhraddin Bahram Shah Mengujek, who highly valued the poem. Quoting Ibn Bibi, he writes:

"In this year (574 AH), Khwaja Nizami Ganjavi, the connoisseur of words, composed the book 'Makhzan al-Asrar' ('The Treasury of Mysteries'), resembling large pearls arranged in verse, and presented it as a gift to the exalted ruler." [5].

Although Nizami intended to travel personally to Erzincan in order to present the book to Bahram Shah, he was unable to do so because military movements had blocked the roads. Consequently, the poet limited himself to sending the manuscript. While dispatching his work, Nizami was aware that the court of Erzincan was surrounded by poets close to the ruler, yet he remained confident in the superiority of his own literary talent. Addressing Bahram Shah, whom he described as "the conqueror of Rum and Abkhazia," the poet declared that the poets of Erzincan would ultimately have to answer before Nizami's genius. [1, 44]. He referred to himself metaphorically as "the owner of a sword forged from words," capable of overcoming all rivals.

In appreciation of the work, Bahram Shah rewarded the poet with five thousand gold dinars, five loaded horses, five mules, and luxurious ceremonial garments. Praising the book highly, the ruler reportedly stated:

"If it were possible, I would send an immense treasure as a reward for this book, whose verses are arranged like pearls. Through this work, my name will live forever in the world."

These words clearly demonstrate Bahram Shah's foresight and the high value he placed upon literature and art. [5].

The poet's second major work was *Khosrow and Shirin*, which is distinguished by the originality of its dedications and panegyrics. In fact, the poem was composed in honor of Shamsaddin Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan, the second ruler of the Azerbaijani Atabegs and the actual sovereign authority of the period. However, since the last Seljuk ruler of Iran, Toghrul III, still nominally retained the title of sultan, the work was formally dedicated to him. Although in these dedications Toghrul is referred to as the "Sultan" and Atabeg Muhammad as the "naib-e sultan" (deputy of the sultan), the text itself clearly reveals who the true ruler was considered to be.

The poet's praise is directed toward the "just sultan," described as the "protector of the realm" and the "lord of the world," yet the essence of the poem consists of advice addressed to the great Atabeg, portrayed as the "leader of kings" who had "saved the world from oppression." Nizami emphasizes the unparalleled power of this ruler, stating that no other man of equal strength had been born. According to the poet, "from Abyssinia to China all lands opened before this statesman; while raising the cup in Iraq, he inspired fear in Rum and Syria; Abkhazia and Derbent were his hunting grounds; and he was the one who attacked Khwarazm and Samarkand, conquered territories from Ganja to Khuzistan, and rode from Oman to Isfahan." [1, 94] Mammad Said Ordubadi writes that although the poem *Khosrow and Shirin* was originally

composed at the request of Toghrul III, after the ruler's imprisonment it was presented to Qizil Arslan. [3,140]. Meanwhile, the orientalist Yevgeny Bertels notes that Nizami dedicated the poem simultaneously to three rulers: the Iraqi Seljuk Toghrul III (1177–1194), the Eldiguzid ruler Shamsaddin Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan (1174–1186), and his brother Qizil Arslan, who had not yet ascended the throne at that time. [6, 42]

Bertels further records that as soon as the ruler heard of Nizami's arrival, he hurriedly ordered the wine to be removed and the music and singing to be stopped. According to Nizami, the sultan explained this order by saying that Nizami's poetry was sweeter than any music, and that where such poetry existed, music itself became unnecessary. [6, 43] This episode clearly demonstrates the ruler's deep respect and admiration for the poet. Nizami himself describes the meeting in the following lines:

*“Entering the court, the messenger announced:
‘My Shah, the river has arrived at the sea.’”*

Şəkil 1. Nizami Gəncəvi Atabəy Qızıl Arslanın qəbulunda. 1481-ci ilə aid əlyazmadan miniatür. Uolters Sənət Muzeyi.

During the meeting, when Nizami Ganjavi attempted to bow before the ruler, the shah descended from his throne and warmly embraced the poet. They greeted one another like long-separated friends, after which the ruler seated Nizami beside him. [4, 69] The poet then offered advice to the young shah, speaking about the proper treatment of the people, the hardships faced by ordinary subjects, and the principles of governance. He also supported his counsel with examples drawn from history. This episode demonstrates that Nizami possessed not only literary authority but also considerable moral and social influence among the population. People burdened by taxes, debts, and conflicts with officials would come to him seeking guidance and advice. His fellow citizens addressed him respectfully as “Sheikh” and regarded his residence as a place of refuge. Even today, people living in Ganja and its surrounding regions frequently visit Nizami's tomb and seek spiritual comfort through reverence for their “Sheikh.”

According to Yevgeny Bertels, after this journey Nizami's fame spread not only among urban intellectual circles but also throughout feudal courts and palaces. Two years later, another ruler, Akhsitan I, appealed to the poet with a request for a new poem. In May 1188, a messenger arrived at Nizami's modest home carrying a letter from the Shirvanshah. The commission was clearly stated: the ruler wished the poet to compose, for the first time in Persian, the famous Arab legend about the tragic love between Majnun and the beautiful Leyli. [6, 46] At first, Nizami hesitated to accept the request. The Shirvanshah, who considered himself of Persian origin, had

expressed contempt for the Turkish language, claiming that composing the poem in Turkish would diminish the dignity of literature. This attitude toward the poet's native language deeply affected Nizami.

After completing his final poem, Iskandarnama, Nizami addressed paternal advice to his son Muhammad. The aging poet encouraged both his son and the younger generation to pursue knowledge, virtue, and wisdom. While finishing the first part of the poem, a devastating earthquake struck Ganja in 1192, causing widespread destruction in the city that the poet deeply loved. Historical sources also confirm the severity of this disaster. The Azerbaijani Atabeg ruler Malik Izzaddin assisted in rebuilding the city, and out of gratitude and respect, Nizami dedicated his work to him. [4, 71]

There is no direct historical record indicating whether the fourth Atabeg, Nusrataddin Abu Bakr, granted Nizami a "gift of the pen" for Iskandarnama. Nevertheless, considering that the ruler himself was a poet and was praised by Nizami Ganjavi for his enlightenment and appreciation of learning, it would be unfair to assume that he remained indifferent toward the "first and chosen nightingale of the dynastic rose garden." This view is confirmed by the verses dedicated by the poet to the ruler in Sharafnama, the first part of Iskandarnama. Addressing Atabeg Nusrataddin Abu Bakr, Nizami writes: "If Shirvanshah Akhsitan nurtured me with blessings and raised me from earth to the heavens, you honored me even more greatly and exalted me higher than he did." [1, 95-96]

Mammad Amin Rasulzade notes that these verses leave little doubt that, just as Nizami had received patronage from Akhsitan I, he likewise received literary rewards from Atabeg Nusrataddin.

Further evidence appears in a fourteenth-century manuscript copy of the "Khamsa," purchased in Paris by Mehmet Meherram. In the section entitled Khatam-e Kitab of the Iqbalnama, a detail absent from printed editions is mentioned. According to this account, Nusrataddin Abu Bakr, being extremely pleased with the work, immediately presented Nizami with one thousand pure gold dinars. In addition, he bestowed valuable gifts including riding animals, silk, fine fabrics, and other luxurious items, along with a royal robe of honor. Moreover, by an official decree issued through the divan, the poet was granted an annual stipend of two hundred gold coins. [1, 96]

Possessing a strong sense of dignity and self-respect, Nizami maintained his historical and moral position throughout his life and never humiliated himself before anyone. Even when composing panegyrics or making requests to rulers, he regarded himself as their equal. Drawing strength from his rich inner world, the poet addressed rulers almost like a father offering advice to his sons, guiding them toward justice and righteousness. A clear example of this attitude appears in the preface to Leyli and Majnun, where he offers moral counsel to Akhsitan I. In this "Book of Advice," Nizami appeals to the ruler with the following words:

"Be powerful, but do not lose your restraint. Drink wine, but do not become intoxicated. Do not allow hypocrites near you. Fulfill your promises in order to gain the trust of the people. Do not trust those whom your heart does not accept. Never underestimate your enemy. If you must strike, strike at the root; but if you seize someone, do not humiliate them." [1, 98]

Conclusion

The presented research evaluates the personality of Nizami Ganjavi, the appreciation shown to him by the rulers of his time, and the manner in which creative figures gathered around him and benefited from his intellectual influence. These issues have been analyzed on the basis

of the poet's own poems as well as studies conducted in literary scholarship. The correspondence and relationships of the great poet with the prominent personalities of his era have attracted considerable interest not only in literary studies but also in historical research. By examining these correspondences and approaching the poems as historical sources, scholars gain the opportunity to explore not only the political views of the rulers of the period, but also their scientific knowledge and worldview. All these aspects contribute significantly to historians' understanding and reconstruction of the historical and cultural environment of the twelfth and thirteenth centuries.

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